

The Rise of Epigraphic Compacts in Medieval South India

Introduction

This essay, keeping with the theme of moving beyond older models of kingship, will examine the history of “political compacts” in later Chola (Cōla) and post Chola times. By the term “political compacts” I refer to publicly inscribed pledges of loyalty and mutual solidarity among lesser lords or corporate groups. Focusing mostly on central and north-central lands of the Chola empire, it will suggest that the appearance and rise of such compacts from the twelfth century, usually read as a symptom of the fragmentation of state authority, may be seen in a different light. Scholars have highlighted the connection of these agreements to the rise of new social groups catalyzed by Chola military expansion and agrarian development during the latter half of the twelfth and thirteenth centuries. This essay will further suggest that the rise of “compacts” during later Chola times helps us see how particular “technologies of power” associated with writing expanded during Chola times to new political and social contexts beyond the royal court and Brahmanical assembly.

This essay will build on two related historiographical assumptions. The historiography of early India has tended to imagine states as static administrative structures—characterizing them as centralized, decentralized, segmentary, processual, even feudal. These typologies have been helpful in understanding significant aspects of the organization of power and the operation of political dynamics. But to the extent that they have tended to understand the state as an administrative abstraction, they have also contributed to a blindness toward the “actions of the state.” In moving away from such models, I do not suggest that medieval polities were arbitrary, despotic entities, or may be reduced entirely to the actions of powerful individuals

or personalities. They were characterized by durable practices and relationships, both individual and collective. But these practices, and this is the second assumption of this essay, *constituted* rather than simply signified the state. The “state,” in other words, was itself first and foremost a collection of *practices*. The idea of a practice here should not be confused with the concepts of “ritual” or “symbolic” action as used by many Indian historians and the related ideas of “ritual polity” or “theatre state.” These theorizations make strong distinctions between symbolic, discursive, or rhetorical action on the hand and, “real” or consequential actions on the other. The approach here will regard so-called “ritual” activities in the same analytical field as the “rational” activity of politics and distributive action. Indeed, the barest “furniture” of the state is already thoroughly intertwined with its “symbolic” mode.

The perspective adumbrated above, draws not only on the “anthropology of the state” but, in the Indian context, on an older tradition of immanentist, actionist approaches to the problem of “state formation” as well as those that have moved away from centralized state models, criticized the assumption of bureaucratic rationalities, or refocused attention on court and culture, with the stated purpose of moving a whole host of aesthetic, ritual and symbolic elements back into the realm of contingent historical practice that had earlier been understood as features of a flat dharmic kingship or legitimating aspect of royal authority.¹ The specific focus in this essay will be on the writing of public inscriptions as a technology of power, not merely in the sense that inscriptions, as has long been noted, were indelibly linked to a culture of ritual gift giving that stretched across secular and religious lordships, and were integral in transferring large amounts of wealth between groups and individuals in medieval South India, but that epigraphic protocols evolved into a modality power whose contours from the later Chola period seem to extend beyond the reach of the Chola state.

The Political Implications of Epigraphic Protocols

The sources for this study will be drawn exclusively from the corpus of lithic inscriptions of South India in the Tamil language dating from the latter part of the twelfth, down to the first decades of the fifteenth century. These inscriptions, which cover the walls of hundreds of temples that have survived from the period, have formed the principal source for historians of medieval South India. They were used by earlier generations to reconstruct the political history of the period and more recently by social historians to understand state, society and agrarian relations. This essay will take a different approach,

arguing that inscriptions were not only “records” of financial transaction and legal agreement, not only proclamations of authority, they were also a kind of “technology” of power. To make this point more clearly it will be necessary to outline the main elements of inscriptional practice current during the Chola period. Though writing on permanent materials was put to a great variety of uses in medieval South India, and it is thus not possible to generalize entirely, it would be fair to say that the function of most inscriptions was to record some economic transaction, related to a gift to a religious institution. In most cases these gifts were directed either to communities of Brahman householders or to temples. Inscriptions authorized, commemorated and operationalized these economic transactions. They formed, decrees or proclamations that were binding, at least in part, by their public inditement.

As scholars have noted, the majority of lithic and copper plate inscriptions in South Asia may be divided into two categories: those connected to the orders of kings and those involving transactions by non-royal individuals or corporate bodies.² Royal and non-royal inscriptions in the Chola lands shared the same basic structure.³ They typically begin with some benedictive formulation of auspicious words or symbols and salutation like *svasti śrī* “hail! prosperity!” This is followed by a marking of the regnal year, phrased as “in the x year of the reign of King y.” The king’s name is often accompanied by victorious titles and sometimes a short poetic laud called a *meykkīrtti*. They then introduce the donors or agents of the transaction, which could be a single individual, several individuals, or a corporate body. Places are typically mentioned as descriptors of individual names. The particulars of the transaction are then elaborated in detail. Inscriptions typically conclude with a phrase that the arrangements would “be under the guardianship” of the Śaiva or Vaiṣṇava communities. The arrangement of these inscriptions may be understood as a form of “address.” Their basic structure—commencing with a benediction, followed by date, notification, and concluding exhortation—bears similarity with the arrangement and contents of letters as known from later manuals for scribes. The “addressees” of simple donative epigraphs are not mentioned, but presumably included the parties involved, a putative “public” of property holding lords and men of status, relevant functionaries at religious institutions, as well as presumed “posterity.” The inscriptions of corporate bodies, as we shall see, tend to be the most complex among non-royal inscriptions.

Royal inscriptions have similar structure, but are considerably more elaborate, with stone inscriptions tending to present more abbreviated accounts than the copper plates.⁴ Copper-plate inscriptions, mostly commemorating gifts of land to communities of Brahmans or temples provide a unique picture of the operation of the royal chancellery and the

rituals associated with the implementation of royal orders. These grants were typically bilingual—commencing with Sanskrit, followed by a Tamil portion. In most cases the Sanskrit and Tamil sections mirror one another in basic structure, both conforming to the format mentioned above, and thus are in no way reliant upon one another, each capable of standing on its own. The distinctions between them pertain to their general emphasis. It would seem that the purpose of the Sanskrit portion was primarily laudatory, containing an elaborate eulogy of the Chola family and its ancestors; its rendition of the “notification” portion of the grant is highly abbreviated, and compared to the Tamil portion, seems essentially perfunctory.⁵ The Tamil portion, by contrast, contains a brief formulaic eulogy of the commanding king, but includes an expanded notification of the details of the land grant, its conditions, donees, and, importantly for our purposes, a more or less elaborate account of its draft and execution. In the case of one of the most detailed of these orders, the famous Tiruvalaṅkāṭu plates, the Tamil portion presents a highly complex document which records its own history and protocol in some detail.⁶ It begins with a benediction followed by the date and place of its issuance, as an order from the mouth of the king while he was in his palace in Muṭiḱoṅṭaĉōlapuram, becoming henceforward known as *tirumukam*, literally “auspicious mouth” addressed to local notables and all residents of surrounding towns and villages. After adumbrating the basic elements of the order, noting that it had been registered in the royal accounts (a process more detailed in other grants, and indicating numerous specialized offices for recording tax related matters), and appointing an overseer of its implementation, the document then shifts perspective, marking the date once again, and adding a royal eulogy, but now from the place of the locality, where the order states that it had arrived and been respectfully received and honored by local district elites (*nāṭṭār*). These men then accompanied a female elephant around the boundaries of the gifted land and then drew up and gave the deed, the specific privileges of which are provided in considerable detail, to the god Śiva at Tiruvalaṅkāṭu. The document is concluded by noting that the stipulations of the order were duly entered into the temple accounts, and providing an extensive list of “signatories,” including the king’s men, local notables, arbitrators, accountants, and scribes. The engraver of the grant is noted, but there appears to be no concluding benediction or imprecation, as was otherwise common practice. The inscribed copper plates were perforated and threaded by a copper ring joined by a seal with royal insignia and a Sanskrit verse identifying the document as an order *śāsana* of the king.

Distinct in complexity from the donative inscriptions of individuals and the more elaborate royal inscriptions were epigraphs representing the actions of local collective bodies. Since Pallava times, groups of men associated with

temples (*tānattār*) but particularly those who formed the leaders of Brahman settlements (*mahāsabhaiyār*), came together and issued inscriptions similar in format to those mentioned above. These assemblies were on the one hand formally distinct from the state—in that they could issue proclamations, alienate lands as tax-free, and make other decisions independent of the royal court, and their functioning operated continuously across the vicissitudes of dynastic rule.⁷ Nilakanta Sastri regarded them as the apex of a vast and complex associational life, both voluntary and hereditary, that formed the sinews of “local government” during Pallava and Chola times (Nilakanta Sastri 1932: 107). Having said this, it should not be forgotten that the very existence of these inscriptions representing the actions and proclamations of local groups emerge from what may have earlier been entirely oral, palm leaf, or even unrecorded protocols during the expansion of the Pallava state into the countryside, and the shift to public writing on monuments was quite possibly through the mimicry of royal grants.

Both royal and non-royal inscriptions outlined above, considered the permanent versions of more ephemeral records, have been understood as primarily “documentary” in nature. Dismissing the eulogistic preambles to the inscriptions, where they exist, as exaggerated literary bombast (though using them extensively to reconstruct dynastic history), historians conceived of the remaining parts of the inscriptions as legal and administrative. This understanding, shared across a variety of interpretations, has been strongly connected to the idea of the state as an “administrative structure.” Inscriptions understood in this way have been used to theorize key features of the Chola state and its fiscal structure, on the one hand, or alternately, in the case of inscriptions of village bodies like *mahāsabhās*, “local government” on the other. While inscriptions do indeed provide the only surviving evidence of the nomenclature of taxation, titles of royal servants, local notables, among much other very useful information, such interpretations have been somewhat indifferent to the procedural elements encoded in inscriptions. To the extent that such elements have been taken up at all, they have generally been assumed to be nothing more than the office protocol for a Chola “tax department,” “state bureaucracy” or committee-based local government. Yet James Heitzman, in his important study of the Chola state, warned against interpreting the “offices” mentioned in inscriptions as a part of a state bureaucracy. While recognizing the growth and proliferation of officials connected to tax collection in the eleventh century, Heitzman pointed out that most of them were land-owning elite or had “positions and influence [that] owed little to bureaucratic function, resting instead on their own personal power bases and influence at court” (Heitzman 1997: 159). Given the absence of rationalized bureaucratic offices, and that “service” was not “public” but

obtained among property holding elites, eminent families, or individual lords, it may be further suggested that the practices of revenue collection and administration were founded on relations of hierarchy underwritten by what Heitzman termed “ritual polity.”

Sheldon Pollock, apparently in rebuttal to the dismissal of inscriptional eulogies as largely irrelevant, has suggested (borrowing from Heidegger and Lacapra) that we conceive of inscriptions as divided between symbolic, “reality enhancing” discourse embodied in the aestheticized, “workly” poetic preambles in Sanskrit on the one hand, and the quotidian, univocal, and everyday “non-Sanskrit” “documentary” portions of the grant, on the other (Pollock 1996: 242). This laudable attempt to rescue the eulogistic poems from irrelevance has had the unfortunate effect of also assigning to the “grant” portions of the inscriptions a status very similar to their role in the very historiography he wishes to move beyond—where the quotidian language of the state was “informational,” “documentary,” and devoid of “performative and symbolic meaning.” Yet, if we approach the “documentary” portions of the inscriptions, following frameworks suggested by Inden and Heitzman, without the idea that they express a self-evident administrative language, it will be clear that even the most quotidian aspects of state action were already replete with “performative and symbolic meaning”. In fact, it is the performance of the epigraphic donation or order, both in its transcription as an “address” to a putative public, as well as its ritualized enunciation and reception, that distinguished it from simple, direct discourse. What I am suggesting is that the so-called “administrative” or “documentary” idiom of inscriptions was already distinct from everyday language, was highly formulaic, and was imbued with an aura of power. Sometimes orders were further sanctified by a literary encomium that had its own courtly aesthetic style, but that even these eulogistic poems, I believe, were substantially solemnized by their association with the protocols of the epigraph rather than the other way around.

We have seen already that both non-royal and royal inscriptions take the form of public addresses, or enunciations, pertaining to binding agreements of various kinds pertaining to the distribution of goods and services relating to religious institutions. To what degree they were “consulted” and connected to more ephemeral documents kept on the part of the royal court and religious institutions, are important questions partially addressed by scholarship but which still require further research.⁸ But whatever their referential use, their creation was part of a linguistic and somatic performance which both distinguished them from everyday quotidian communication and imbued them with social power. These protocols were both associative and enunciative in nature. Non-royal gifts seem to have been simple, perhaps involving a single

moment of proclamation, perhaps at the moment of inditement itself. Inscriptions of corporate groups present a more complex protocol. In *mahāśabhā* inscriptions from the tenth-century, for example, we find variously recounted men coming together in assemblies, deciding resolutions, making orders, transcriptions by scribes and *madhyasthas*, and acknowledgement by men of the *ūr*.⁹ In the case of the elaborate royal orders, the procedures were even more complex. In the case of inscriptions like the Tiruvalaṅkāṭu plates and Ulagalanda Perumal temple inscription (see note 4), the sections of the “text” as they stand represent different “documentary” moments. Protocols at court like petitioning, royal utterance, the appointment of an executor are noted in detail and the reception, veneration, proclamation and ritual procession of the order—understood as an embodiment of the king’s oral presence—in the locality, as well as its specification and notation in local archives, witnessing, and finally its engraving in stone or copper, are all recorded, often with different dates, within the single complex “document.”

Such complexity suggests the existence of some sort of legal framework for the production of state and local documents. This framework may in part be deduced from the śāstric treatises in Sanskrit like *Yājñavalkyaśmṛti* (3rd–5th c. AD) and its later commentaries, particularly that of Vijñāneśvara’s *Mitākṣara* (11th–12th c. AD) composed in the realm of Kalyani Chalukyas (Kalyāṇi Cālukyas), long-term rivals of the Chola kings in the lower Deccan. These texts set out the procedures for drafting copper-plate land grants by kings and a whole host of more ephemeral documents relating to various financial transactions and resolving financial disputes.¹⁰ Yet the epigraphic practices as they evolved in South India cannot be wholly captured by normative Sanskrit texts. In the discussion of royal land grants, for example, both *Yājñavalkya* and Vijñāneśvara are concerned primarily with the elements rather than protocol of the royal order (*śāsana*)—instructing that the king, after having made the gift of land or revenue assignment, should cause a document to be drawn up and copied onto cloth or a copper plate, containing his name along with those of his ancestors, details of the donated gift and its extent, and finally his own signature, date and seal.¹¹ While these elements were surely present in the Chola copper plates (as in those of their contemporaries), the śāstric treatment hardly explains the procedural detail that appears in many Chola royal orders, which, as we have seen above, included an account of the order from its inception to implementation, including its reception, reiteration and witnessing by local notables. The śāstric treatment of non-royal documents, particularly in the *Mitākṣara*’s elaboration, is mostly focused on the drawing up of pledges regarding the payment of debts and special compacts between individuals within the framework of Dharmaśāstric injunctions more generally. The overweening emphasis being

on the language, legibility, witnessing, authentication of the documents and their use as evidence or as a source of binding rules.¹² Here we see a greater emphasis on protocol, but interestingly, these documents—perhaps precisely because of the often temporary nature of such agreements—are not conceived of as being engraved on permanent materials. Their proclamatory function seems to have been limited to the parties concerned and local adjudicants. Such texts, as Nilakanta Sastri observed some time ago his study of Uttaramērūr, provide little light even on the activities of brahmanical bodies like the *mahāśabhā*, not to mention other social spheres. He opined that “there was no written law or even a distinctly formulated principle intended to govern the conduct” of the *mahāśabhā* with local groups, both being embedded in a “veritable network of diverse jurisdictions and liberties not always clearly marked off from one another” (Nilakanta Sastri 1932: 106-107). From this perspective, the śāstric “legal framework” that underpinned epigraphic documentary practice of such corporate groups was of a very general nature. Inscriptions present a world of far more diverse protocols, and one that in no way aligns neatly with śāstric norms—suggesting instead, what Don Davis has called an “intermediate realm of law” (Davis 2005). Scholars are only beginning to theorize more analytically complex relationships between the realm of *dharmaśāstra* and epigraphic practice, particularly as they obtained among growing numbers of corporate groups in medieval India (see Davis 2005; Lubin 2018a and 2018b).

If there was any commonality to these epigraphic protocols, it would be that the inclusion of writing on permanent materials themselves as part of the process of decision making formed a kind “technology of power” through a series of verbal formulae and ritualized actions which effectively imbued them with binding force, a protocol of formalized speech in the context of some mediated “public” or collective sociality. It is this interface between the collective sociality whereby an agreement was made, a resolution announced or even a gift proclaimed, and the technology of writing on stone that makes inscriptions distinctive forms of evidence for the as yet unwritten history of sociability in medieval South Asia.

Two features were crucial to this protocol; the conceptualization of the inscription as an “address” or “enunciation” to a putative public of interested parties both in the present and future, and relatedly, the performative and discursive production of “presence” necessary for this enunciatory moment. We have mentioned the features of inscriptions as “address” above, but crucial to the enunciatory effect was the staging of “presence” or “voice”—by which I mean a kind of temporal-spatial *mise en scène* in which the actions of individuals and groups were solemnized through enunciation or proclamation. While for epigraphists and historians such elements of inscriptions may seem

almost too banal to merit comment, it is worth considering the implications of such verbal formula. This was achieved very minimally by the dating of inscriptions which placed social agents in a particular place and time, and more emphatically by the benedictive “calling out” or “hailing” which prefaced every inscription. For Brahmanical *mahāsabhās* and royal courts this staging was more elaborate, often involving meeting, resolution, command and deputation—all represented within and culminating with a command or resolution inscribed in public.

The most elaborate inscriptional staging of voice and presence is to be found, perhaps not surprisingly, in royal orders, which often provide very particular details of the time and location (even down to palace, chamber and/or seat) from where the king’s command was first uttered, and use the first person plural pronominal suffix for verbs related to the will of the king regarding elements of the royal order.¹³ In copper plates (and some *mahāsabhā* inscriptions) we also encounter the reception of the order—conceived as an extension of the king’s presence—as a ritualized act represented in the inscription through the local “voice.” The epigraphic account of the locality leaders greeting the order is not simply a description, but also a scene where the “presence” or “immediacy” of the actors is signaled by the use of personal pronominal suffixes, to give the sense of “We the elders of the *nāṭu*, seeing the order, rose up and went out to meet it, paying it homage, receiving it and placing it on our heads.”¹⁴ We thus hear the voice of the king locality and village elites within a single document. So, while royal orders on the one hand formed a visible manifestation of Chola authority in the countryside, their protocols reveal that they were also dialogical practices, involving the collective participation of rural elites within this lordship. But even the most modest donative inscription, by virtue of its verbal formula—its benediction, salutation, self-proclaimed spatio-temporal marking and exhortation—conjured a putative public within which it situated itself. In this way, the practice of issuing inscriptions—beyond the very real material relations they created through the transfer of goods and services—had what Althusser called an ideologically “interpellative” aspect, in that their projected “setting,” the assumed “audiences” of their enunciations, both present and future, shaped the agentive subjectivity of the donors and participants.

Technologies of Presence Beyond the Court

My contention thus far has been that the so called quotidian, “administrative” language and protocol of Chola inscriptions constituted a discourse of power, the distinctive feature of which was the staging of “presence” or

“immediacy” through various verbal formula and linguistic conventions. Brahmanical and imperial inscriptions encoded particularly elaborate protocols which, among other conventions, identified the royal order with the aura of the monarch himself.

In the second half of this paper I would like to turn to a particular use of inscriptions by individuals and groups outside of the Chola court and Brahmanical establishment during the later Chola empire and after. Chola political successes and agrarian transformations throughout the eleventh century created the conditions for the rise of new groups and substantial agrarian change—chief among which were the emergence of new classes of dominant landowners and the incorporation of non-agrarian peoples into agrarian society, sometimes through military service, and the formation, particularly towards the end of the empire, of corporate groups of cultivator peasants and artisans. One striking epigraphic development that accompanied these changes in the later empire was the use of stone temple inscriptions to record political “compacts”—agreements among individuals and groups that celebrated bonds of solidarity and exhorted all parties to remain loyal and protect each other’s interests at all costs, even by the use of force. These compacts were first noticed by K.A. Nilakanta Sastri and have since formed the subject of an important scholarly article by Noboru Karashima.¹⁵

Most of the compacts between individuals date from the latter half of the twelfth century and first half of the thirteenth, but the earliest inscriptions of this nature date to the closing years of the reign of the great king Kulōttuṅka I (Kulōttuṅga 1070–1120) and his son Vikramacōla (1118–1135). They appear on a temple in Sivapuri (in modern Ramnathapuram district) in the southern region of the former Pandya (Pāṇḍya) kingdom, which for much of the eleventh century had been ruled through a Chola vice-royalty (usually a member of the Chola royal family). During the reign of Kulōttuṅka I, however, Chola grip on this region began to slip substantially: the Chola vice-royalty seems to have come to an end and Pandya kings rose up against Kulōttuṅka, with the Cholas only being able to retain a presence in several garrison towns. It is in this politically tumultuous environment that we encounter two unusual inscriptions at Sivapuri. In the first, dated to the forty-second year of Kulōttuṅka’s reign (1112) one Kaṇṭan Maṅkalattēvaṅ also known as Tuvarāpati-vēlaṅ, swore a vow of alliance and fealty to Sundarattōḷan Kaṇṭan, who had the title of Rājendracōla Tuvarāpati-vēlaṅ, by saying:

I, Kaṇṭan Maṅkalattēvaṅ also known as Tuvarāpati-vēlaṅ, do hereby swear that I shall remain true to (your) life, wealth and honour, and that if I fail, I shall incur the sin of him who becomes the husband of his mother, and of consuming liquor and beef.¹⁶

Some ten years later, another inscription from the same temple records another profession of loyalty in similar language by one Rājendracōḷaṅ also known as Niṣadarājaṅ towards Kaṅṭaṅ Sundarattōḷaṅ known as Tuvarāpati-vēḷaṅ (ARE 1929, No. 55). The specific contextual significance of these rather enigmatic inscriptions is difficult to understand, though three other slightly later inscriptions involving individuals with similar personal names and sharing the title Tuvarāpati-vēḷaṅ, appear on the same temple, but are dated to the reign of a Pandya king by the name of Jaṭāvarmaṅ Śrīvallaḅha, who likely took up arms against Kulōttuṅka I and his successors and was recognized widely in areas south of Madurai.¹⁷ Judging from their titles, these men seem to have been landholders of local importance, likely affiliating themselves somehow with the Chola court until the end of Kulōttuṅka's reign, when they faced some uncertainties requiring mutual allegiance among themselves, before finding their place again in the new political environment of a resurgent Pandya king.¹⁸

The remaining inscriptions, mostly dated to the reigns of the Chola monarchs Rājādhiraḅa II (1163–1179), Kulōttuṅka III (1178–1218), and Rājarāja III (1216–1260), are found for the most part in the central and northern reaches of the Chola empire from Cholamandalam (Cōḷamaṅṭalam) and Tondaimandalam (Toṅṭaimaṅṭalam). They are mostly issued by local lords or “chiefs.” Some of these locality chiefs claimed descent from smaller ancient lineages that had been integrated into the Chola military establishment, while others, coming from upland dry zone warrior groups, were clearly new on the scene, but shared a similar trajectory of service and ennoblement through military service. The most powerful among these chiefs were the Kāḍavarāyars (Kāṭavarāyars), Sambuvarāyars (Campuvarāyas), Vānakovarāyars (Vānakōvarāyars) and Malaiyamāns (Malaiyamaṅs). Beginning in the early twelfth century, these chiefs, along with local notables and titled land-owning men, appear in inscriptions making public vows of loyalty to one another and sometimes to the Chola monarch himself.

The inscriptions have a similar format, beginning with benediction and announcement of the date in the regnal year of the Chola king. Then, like the Sivapuri inscriptions quoted above, they typically shift immediately into the voice of one or more of the concerned parties, who introduce themselves and announce that on a particular date a document was engraved in stone with various stipulations which form the substance of the compact. In one case from Tiruvannamalai, dated to the 27th year of Kulōttuṅka III's reign (A.D. 1205), some ten Sambuvarāya and Cētirāya nobles are listed with full titles, after which the inscription reads “we, these persons, agreed among ourselves that the following was to be inscribed.”¹⁹ The substance of these compacts, also iterated in the first person as “he and I” or “we,” was essentially

a profession of loyalty—that the concerned chiefs and nobles would promote and defend their mutual (and now collective) interests to one another and/or a third party (often the king) by use of force, if necessary, and often against particular individuals. The Tiruvannamalai inscription stipulates that:

We will never go against the orders of the king and will perform them as Cētirāya (*cetirāya*) is pleased to order and not do the work of Makataināṭālvāṇ also known as Vānakōvaraiyaṇ and Kulōttuṅkacōla Kōvaraiyaṇ, nor act as secretaries (*olaiyātal*), messengers (*pokakkāṭṭatal*), allies (*uṛavupaṇṇatal*), or conclude agreements (*aruṭi ceytal*) for them or their people [...] (SII 8, N° 106).

The emphasis on solidarity was expressed through taking one’s allies interests as one’s own. An inscription from Thanjavur, dated to the reign of Rājarāja III, and after swearing allegiance to the king, puts it succinctly:

One who becomes an enemy of any one of us shall be the enemy of all three of us; and one who becomes a friend of one of us shall be the friend of all three of us.²⁰

The “substance” of the compact is typically concluded by a claim that persons present consented to its terms and had it engraved on the temple, and in some cases presented a document of the compact to all parties concerned.²¹ Several (but by no means all) inscriptions mention the performance of solemnizing rituals like the licking of ghee from the *abhiṣeka* ceremony at the temple or invoking spirits (*bhūta*) and sacrificing animals to accompany the compacts, but this does not seem to be consistent.²² Finally, many of the inscriptions conclude with imprecations. Imprecations, similar in function to the ubiquitous statements that placing temple gifts under the protection of the Maheśvaras and Vaiṣṇavas, had been traditional parts of land grants issued by kings since the later Gupta period, presenting curses to those that might violate the terms of the grants. The compacts examined here, which seem to have taken place under conditions of political duress and uncertainty, refer to violation of terms as *droha* or disloyalty (a term *not* used in traditional inscriptional imprecations). Nilakanta Sastri, reading these imprecations some time ago, noted that they were often so “shocking” as to be better passed over rather than translated (Nilakanta Sastri 1955: 375). More recently, Noboru Karashima has analyzed these imprecations and noted they often took on a highly specific character, introducing new and more particular curses that would befall the oath-breaker (Karashima 2009: 261-273). These ranged from having to carry the betel box and sandals of one’s enemies, or having to drink from the spittoon of one’s servants, to growing breasts together with heavy facial hair.

Scholars beginning with Nilakanta Sastri have rightly understood the appearance of such compacts as evidence for the gradual collapse of Chola imperial authority, first in the crucially strategic and long-held regions of

Tondaimandalam and Naduvil Nadu, but by the reign of Rājarāja III, even within the Chola heartland itself (Nilakanta Sastri 1955: 407-408, 426-428). Indeed, from the reign of Kulōttuṅka III (1178–1218) various southern Pandya kings repeatedly vanquished Chola armies and the Chola king had to seek security from the Hoysaḷas of Dorasamudra, who were keen to expand their influence in the south. The situation was even more drastic in the reign of Rājarāja III (1216–1260), when the Chola monarch, fleeing a Pandya army, was captured and held in Sengamangalam by his erstwhile subordinate, the Kāḍava chieftain Kōpperuñcinṅkaṅ, obtaining release only after Hoysaḷa intervention. In this general context, the appearance of compacts between local lords, even if dated in the reign of a Chola monarch or professing loyalty to the crown, as most of them do, signified for Nilakanta Sastri, the growth of *imperium in imperio* within the Chola empire, eventually leading to its collapse as smaller kingdoms “burst the shell” of imperial control (*ibid.* 1955: 407).

While the reading of these inscriptions as symptoms of failing Chola authority is surely correct, it must be kept in mind that these chiefs, in many cases, were not, strictly speaking, refractory subordinates. Compacts were dated in the reigns of Chola monarchs and often explicitly professed loyalty to the king. Nevertheless, they represent something new. Chola subordinates in earlier times (even in moments of imperial weakness) had never used public proclamations to express their loyalty to one another or to the crown. There are of course epigraphic representations of fealty and the conveyance of honours to subordinates (most often occurring in the descriptive eulogies of ruling kings), but political relations were essentially constituted at court (or on the battlefield) and through protocols which, it would seem, did not use such written compacts, preferring instead the traditional instruments like tribute, marriage and gift exchange.²³ These political compacts thus represent, not only, as Nilakanta Sastri pointed out, that the Chola court could no longer guarantee and protect the interests of its subordinates, who were forced to act independently, but that they deployed a novel medium to establish and secure these relations—written and publicly inscribed compacts. These compacts were engraved in temples, which makes them even more anomalous, as they do not seem to form part of the transactional economies of the temples on which they were inscribed.²⁴ It would seem that by the twelfth century, the inscriptional habit and the temple had become so significant in the political sphere that temple walls seemed the most suitable place for the mutual profession of loyalty between two notables or chiefs.

Furthermore, like imperial and Brahmanical orders, the compacts present complex temporalities that are woven together through different registers of presence effected by individual and collective voice. Indeed, as proclamations of agreements, it was necessary for such inscriptions to record the assent of

all parties. According to the inscriptions themselves, this was achieved either through a meeting or the presentation of the agreement as a document to all parties. The inscriptions thus present a twofold temporality: first, an occasion when members of one or more parties, having agreed among themselves, assembled to have the compact engraved, or presented the written compact to parties not present; and second, the operative part of the compact itself, which encodes a moment of profession of loyalty and solidarity in the first person singular or plural voice. Obviously central to these inscriptions was the protocol of meetings and gatherings, the history of which remains almost entirely unwritten in precolonial India, and an area where much research is yet to be conducted.²⁵ What we may suggest for the moment is that these compacts solemnized and formalized such agreements (hitherto unrecorded) by using traditional epigraphic conventions associated with royal gifts like the staging of presence and the invocation of generalized curses to specific ends. The epigraphic conventions of royal and Brahmanical prerogative become appropriated by new social agents.

I would now like to turn to another set of inscriptions, solidarity compacts among corporate groups. The emergence of new corporate groups during Chola times has been well-established and remains one of the enduring features of the social history of medieval south India. These groups had their genesis in the eleventh and twelfth centuries. The most precocious and prominent among these groups in the epigraphic records, and on whom I have written elsewhere, were the supra-local trading associations like the *aiññūrruvar*, whose span both geographically and temporally stretched beyond the Chola empire, but which from the eleventh appear in inscriptions bedecked with eulogies, visual paraphernalia, and operational protocols for assembly and proclamation that closely mirrored those of royal courts.²⁶ Another sphere of corporate life that emerges in the later Chola period is that occupied by the famous *valāṅkai* and *iṭāṅkai* or “right-hand” and “left-hand” divisions. These groups, originating as nominations of the contingents of the Chola army, became imbricated in the gradual and complex social transformation of non-agricultural peoples into Chola agrarian society in the twelfth century, often through forms of cultivation and land ownership (see Subbarayalu 2012: 168-175). The emergence of these groups was in fact not unrelated to same social processes that saw proliferation of chiefs in the final century of the Chola empire. Subbarayalu has shown that *iṭāṅkai* and *valāṅkai* in the thirteenth-century inscriptions seemed to denote supra-local corporate organizations composed of individual regional and caste sub-groups, and seem to be greatly concerned with the protection of collective interests. We have a number of unpublished thirteenth-century solidarity “pacts” issued by these groups, which provide origin myths, assert rights and claim

prerogative over social interactions of their heterogeneous membership.²⁷ In one often cited inscription from Ūṭṭattūr, after recounting an origin myth for the *iṭāṅkai* peoples, the inscription announces that:

We, members of the ninety-eight sub-groups of the *iṭāṅkai*, enter into a compact that we shall hereafter behave like sons of the same parents, and what good and evil will befall us will be shared by all. If anything derogatory happens to the *Idāṅgai* [*iṭāṅkai*] class, we will jointly assert our rights till we establish them. It is also understood that only those who, during their congregational meetings to settle communal disputes, display the *birudas* of horn, bugle and parasol shall belong to our class. Those who must recognise us now and hereafter, in public, must do so from our distinguishing symbols—the feather of the crane and the loose-hanging hair. The horn and the conch-shell shall also be sounded in front of us and the bugle blown according to the fashion obtaining among *Idāṅgai* [*iṭāṅkai*] people. Those who act in contravention to these rules shall be treated as enemies of our class. Those who behave differently from the rules prescribed for the conduct of *Idāṅgai* [*iṭāṅkai*] classes shall be excommunicated and shall not be recognized as *Śrutimāns*. They will be considered slaves of the classes who are opposed to us.²⁸

This inscription bears some striking resemblances to the “political” compacts examined above between Chola subordinates. The inscription uses a collective first person voice to both introduce and present the substance of the oath. Like the chiefly compacts, the notion of immediacy is crucial to these epigraphic representations. The conception of loyalty is also quite similar, as an almost empathetic entailment, where common interests and group honor were to be safeguarded at all times. They also share a concern with disloyalty, and set out specific punishments that were to be meted out against those who violated the terms of the compact. What is distinctive in these compacts is the concern of expressing creating group solidarity not only through the compact itself, but through public display of various symbols—the crane feather, the loose hanging hair, and particularly musical instruments to be sounded when the sub-groups walked in procession. These concerns over marching insignia and musical style suggest the participation in a public protocol of processions that may be traced back to Chola times and clearly put forward a courtly register, as processions were a regular and important part of royal life in the Chola empire.

A final set of inscriptions come down to us from the same regions of central northern Tamil Nadu from where many of the earlier solidarity pacts have been found, but date from the fifteenth century, almost one hundred and fifty years after the collapse of the Chola empire and during a period of substantial incursion of northern warrior groups (*nāyakas*) into Tondaimandalam following the campaigns of the Vijayanagara king Kampaṇṇa against the Sambuvarāyars

at the end of the fourteenth century. Several inscriptions dated to the early fifteenth century speak of a revolt of *iṭaṅkai* and *valaṅkai* cultivating groups against land holders and state officers. Noboru Karashima and Y. Subbarayalu, once again, have offered us a complete study of this event, based on the analysis of over 25 mostly unpublished inscriptions from north central Tamil Nadu ranging from approximately 1404 and 1482 (Subbarayalu 1980 and Karashima 1992: 141-158). It appears to have begun with a coming together of peasant cultivators and artisans—identifying as *iṭaṅkai* and *valaṅkai*—in the year 1429 to protest against landlords, estate holders, royal agents and their armed men in the Vaḷudilampaṭṭu (Vaḷutilampaṭṭu) region of Tondaimandalam, ruled by a Vijayanagar-appointed governor, over the issue of excessive tax-revenue burdens borne by these lower castes. Largely identical compacts of solidarity were drawn up and inscribed at the same time in the first month (Cittirai) in the year Saumya (c. March, 1429) in temples at Aduthurai, Kil-paluvur, Vridhachalam and Pennadam.²⁹ They read something like:³⁰

Hail! Prosperity! In the year Saumya, on 16 Cittirai, we the people of the *valaṅkai* 98 and *iṭaṅkai* 98 of the Vaḷudilampaṭṭu province (*ucāvaṭi*), having assembled (*irantu*) in full strength in the meeting pavilion (*tirukaṭṭalai*) of the Śiva temple in Viṭṭaparru-Ukaḷḷūr-kūrṛram (...) let the following be engraved: In this *maṅṭalam* even if the provincial governor (*ucāvaṭi pradhāni*), the military people (*vāṇṇiyar*), and tenure holders (*cīvitakāṛar*) coerce us (*nerukkam paṇṇinālum*), or the Brāhmana and Veḷḷāḷa title holders, in collusion with agents of the king, considers us in fault [we shall never submit]. If there appears any one person among us who gives space [to the intruders], slanders us, [violates the grant given by Chikkarasar, or destroys the current measuring rod]³¹, we shall assemble as today and enquire into it. Among those who were born in this *maṅṭalam*, no one should commit treason against the locality (*nāṭṭut turokam*), perform work, make accounts, or write [for the governor and his men?] (...) [Let others write the accounts or collude with the government officers and tenure holders. If there appears one such person, we shall degrade him in the caste hierarchy].

These are in many ways remarkable inscriptions. Most obviously, they form perhaps the only sources from medieval south India discovered to date where we find cultivators and the upper levels of “direct producers” articulating grievances against landlord and the state and seemingly confronting their power.³² The compact is not a set of demands levied against the Vijayanagar state—little in fact is said about the grievances of the *iṭaṅkai* and *valaṅkai*—and historians have had to reconstruct these from other inscriptions related to the movement which name specific taxes and cesses of money, grains and labor.³³ The compacts instead have a twofold purpose: first, to announce the intentions of the dissenting groups to resist cooperation with and coercion by

state agents and the landowning classes who were seen to be colluding with them; but secondly, and even more importantly, to demand compliance on the part of social segments of the *iṭaṅkai* and *valaṅkai* organizations with the stated terms of the compact. Like the chiefly and corporate compacts of the later Chola period, disloyalty (*droha*) to the group (in this case the locality) is mentioned with threats of exclusion.

The “modality” of these inscriptions is also similar to that of the earlier compacts in that they gain their social power, both as proclamations of resistance against the state, and as documents binding members of the *valaṅkai* and *iṭaṅkai* to their terms, from the putative immediacy of the congregation and presence that they enact—“we, members of the *valaṅkai* and *iṭaṅkai*, having assembled in full strength, let the following be engraved” (...) and that in the instance of any of several situations that demanded it, would “assemble as today and enquire into it.” The combination of public assembly, proclamation, and writing made these inscriptions powerful social instruments—a fact all the more significant given that the compacts, in full recognition of the important role of writing and account keeping in the collection of tax revenues, themselves forbid their members from these activities in the service of their social enemies.

We have seen that Chola-period political compacts by chiefs and corporate groups marked a departure from earlier practices of commitments to individual and collective fealty and solidarity which were not typically expressed in the epigraphic medium. These compacts also seem to signal novel uses of the temple as a kind of public—a place where men came together to draft and operationalize alliances between themselves that may have had no specific bearing on the temple economies where they were solemnized and inscribed. It would seem that the collapse of the Chola state only furthered this process. During the peasant disturbances of Tondaimandalam in the fifteenth century reviewed above, the *iṭaṅkai* and *valaṅkai* compacts were simultaneously engraved in four geographically dispersed temples, following meetings assembled in an open space (or *maṅḍapa*) in a part of each temple known as the *tirukaṭṭalai*.³⁴ Given the wide audiences to which these particular inscriptions were aimed, including first and foremost the numerous *jātis* said to comprise the *valaṅkai* and *iṭaṅkai* associations themselves, but also, secondarily (though indirectly), the “antagonists” of these proclamations—elite Brahmanical and land-owning elite, as well as official tenure holders and state agents—suggests that these temples were conceived by the *valaṅkai* and *iṭaṅkai* (and no doubt other social groups implicitly addressed in these inscriptions) as places of “public” association, meeting and record, where the protocols of social power could be enacted, and class struggle, even against the state, could in part be played out.³⁵

Conclusion

I have argued in this essay, partly against recent theories exaggerating the importance of literary encomia as instruments of social power, that the “documentary” portions of inscriptions produced their own aura of authority and should be re-examined in light of recent theories of state. Their connection with protocols of address and assembly, and their discursive staging of immediacy and presence imbued them with binding power authority. This concatenation of power, presence and writing in early medieval South India through the great dynastic agrarian states of the Pallavas, Cholas and Pandyas and their distinctive and tireless use of the epigraphic medium.

I have also suggested in this brief review of political compacts from the later days of the Chola empire, that the epigraphic medium was a complex set of technologies that rising social groups, from aspiring lineages to corporate solidarity groups, were able to make ample use of—through their own mimicry of the protocols typical of the epigraphic habits of Brahmanical and state power—in setting out their own spheres of power seemingly autonomous from the state and its clients when necessary. Indeed, it would seem that one of the great legacies of the state societies of early medieval India was to make public writing, when combined with protocols of association and blessed with the form of durability, into a potentially appropriable technology of power, one that would be eclipsed only by the decline of stone epigraphy and the rise of paper record keeping.

Notes

1. On anthropology of the state which has been almost entirely focused on modern states, see SHARMA & GUPTA 2006. In the context of precolonial Indian history, see INDEN 1990, and, important for this study is HEITZMAN 1997. See also ALAM & SUBRAHMANYAM 1998; ALI 2004; POLLOCK 2006.
2. See SIRCAR 1965: 2; and for South India, HEITZMAN 1997: 143-44.
3. For a basic review of the parts of copper-plate grants, mostly based on Sanskrit inscriptions, see SIRCAR 1965, and CHHABRA 1961.
4. There are of course exceptions, like an early twelfth-century order of Kulōtuṅka I (ARE 1921, No. 39) at the Ulagalanda Perumal (Ulakaḷanta Perumāḷ) temple in Kanchipuram, discussed at length in HEITZMAN & RAJAGOPAL 2004.
5. On the evolving relations of Sanskrit and vernaculars in bilingual south Indian inscriptions, see Francis (forthcoming).
6. SII 3, No. 205. As pointed out by the editor, the Sanskrit portion of the grant was added later to the Tamil document.

7. See the comments of NILAKANTA SASTRI (1932: 96-117) on the *mahāsabhā* of Uttaramerur.
8. For discussions of the production and handling of revenue rolls, see SHANMUGAN 1987.
9. Examples are numerous, but see SII 3, No. 153 and SII 6, No. 345, both relating to Uttaramerur.
10. See the oft-cited passage in *Yājñavalkyasmṛti* 1.318–320 with Vijñāneśvara’s commentary, and the discussion of SIRCAR 1965: 104–106 *et passim* and more recently the translation and discussion of Davis 2018: 511–512. For the use of ephemeral documents relating mostly to debt, financial compacts, and to disputes around default, resolution, ownership and various other issues, see various sections of *Yājñavalkyasmṛti*’s book on the topic of *vyavahāra*.
11. *Yājñavalkyasmṛti* 1.318–320 and comm. Vijñāneśvara clarifies each point but does little by way of expanding the discussion, other than that the document should also exhort future kings to maintain the grant and that a king should have a scribe to take down his orders.
12. See *Yājñavalkyasmṛti* 2.84ff. and 2.185ff. with Vijñāneśvara’s commentary.
13. When not representing the direct voice of the king, royal inscriptions typically refer to the king’s actions by using a verb compounded with the benefactive/honorific auxiliary verb *aruḷ*, “to grace” or “favour”, usually rendered in English as “the king was pleased to x”. See, for example, SII 2.1, rendering Rājarāja I’s order at Thanjavur.
14. SII 3, No. 205. The Tamil text reads *nāṭṭomum tirumukam kaṇṭetireluntu ceṅṅru toḷutu vāṅkit talaimel vaittu*.
15. See the remarks of NILAKANTA SASTRI 1955: 375 *et passim*. The number of these inscriptions, most unpublished, is not entirely clear. Karashima asserts that there are sixteen such inscriptions, though my survey of the sources, which included compacts between landholders as well as chiefs, given that they share the same language and purpose, suggests at least twenty or more. A comprehensive study of such compacts remains a desideratum. See KARASHIMA 2014: 244–245. Published compacts include: SII 2, No. 96; SII 7, No. 119; SII 7, No. 127; SII 8, No. 106; SII 27, No. 245; SII 28, No. 281; and SII 28, No. 286. To these may be added the following unpublished inscriptions: ARE 1908, Nos. 480 and 483; ARE 1919, Nos. 252 and 254; ARE 1921, Nos. 480–481; ARE 1922, No. 56; ARE 1929, Nos. 55 and 65; ARE 1935, No. 189; ARE 1938, Nos. 20, 65 and 502; ARE 1940, No. 100; and ARE 1946, No. 73.
16. ARE 1929, No. 65. I have not been able to consult the transcription of this unpublished inscription and rely on the summary and translation in NILAKANTA SASTRI 1955: 375.
17. SII 14, No. 218; SII 14, No. 242 and SII 14. 243. On the identity of Jāṭavarmaṅ Śrīvalabha, see AYYAR 1962: vi.
18. SII 14, No. 242 records the purchase of lands from the “officials” (*kaṇṁikaḷ*) of one Tēvar Tuvarāpati-veḷaṅ.
19. *Ivvaṅṅavom eṅkalil icaintu kalvetṭiṅa paṭiyāvatu* (SII 8, No. 106).
20. *Eṅkalil oruvaṅṅukku vanta pakai muvomukum pakai āvatākavum oruvarkku vanta uṅṅavu muvarkku uṅṅāvutākavum* (SII 2, No. 96).
21. See the inscription at Tiruvannamalai, which concludes with the statement: “having agreed thus, we persons (iterated above) gave this (document) as inscribed

on the temple of Śiva at Tiruvannamalai” (SII 8, No. 106).

22. These rituals are discussed in KARASHIMA 2014: 247.

23. For a representation of political fealty to the Chola monarch in a tenth century copper plate inscription, see the Udayendiram Plates of the Gaṅga king Pṛthivīpati Hastimalla (SII 2, No. 76).

24. It could be argued that these inscriptions remain transactional, in that some cases a collective consumption of ghee or meat from temple ritual (which presumably would have been commissioned or paid for by the participants) was said to accompany and solemnize the compact, but this is belied by the fact that such rituals are mentioned in only a few cases and even then, seem to play no central role in the epigraphic logic of the compacts.

25. For a treatment of meeting protocols in European history, see VAN VREE & BELL (1999).

26. See ALI 2010. See also KARASHIMA & SUBBARAYALU 2002: 72–78 and RAJAGOPAL 2002: 101–106.

27. ARE 1912, No. 489; ARE 1943–44, No. 276–; and ARE 1940–41, No. 184–. See the discussion in SUBBARAYALU 2012: 171–172, and STEIN 1980: 182–184.

28. ARE 1912, No. 489. As rendered in ARE 1913, Part II, para. 39, and NILAKANTA SASTRI 1955: 551–552 (my additions between square brackets). I have not been able to consult the original text of this unpublished inscription.

29. For Aduthurai, see SII 28, No. 35; for Kil-Paluvur, ARE 1926, No. 253; for Vridhachalam, ARE 1918, No. 92; for Penadadam, ARE 1929, No. 246.

30. I have mostly followed Karashima’s *précis* in which he combined his readings of all of the then-unpublished inscriptions to produce a basic summary. The Aduthurai inscription has since been published (SII 28, No. 35) but the published text seems to contain lacunae as well as passages that Karashima chose to leave out. The published Aduthurai inscription is incomplete and contains some errors in transcription. Brackets indicate passages from Karashima that do not seem to conform to the Aduthurai version.

31. Aduthurai reads *cantācar paṭṭaiyattai kovinātaṅ kālāl irupattunālu aṭiyum vālakkuṭiyaiyum aḷittāl*, of which I am unable to make adequate sense (SII 28, No. 34, ll. 8–9).

32. Later inscriptions from the same region suggest that the *valāṅkai* and *iṭāṅkai* were successful—landlords conceded to their demands and soon joined them to resist the depredations of state agents and official tenure holders, as the unrest spread into the neighboring region between the Kollidam and Kaveri rivers. It was only the emergence of the Nāyaka system in the region in the latter half of the fifteenth century that gradually reduced the revenue burdens on the local population. See the discussions of Karashima and Subbarayalu.

33. See KARASHIMA 1992: 143–151. A remarkable unpublished inscription from Korukkai, south of the Kollidam river (and beyond the Vaḷudilampāṭṭu region), dated some six months after the compacts under question, mentions severe injustices (*aṅṅiyāyam*) faced by *valāṅkai* and *iṭāṅkai* groups and that these groups there considered absconding (the traditional peasant redress to tax depredation) until they heard about events in several *nāṭus* in Vaḷudilampāṭṭu, and then came together to draw up similar compacts.

34. Perhaps a place where performances took place or visitors were fed.

35. I do not mean to suggest that temples were public spaces open to all social groups, particularly the lowest echelons of agricultural labor. In fact, it may be argued

that this publicness only sealed their isolation from the more accepted spaces of public discourse, where writing and power came together.

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Abstract

This essay examines the history and significance of political compacts among local lords, vassals and corporate groups in medieval South India. Focusing mostly on inscriptional records from the central and north-central lands of the Chola empire, from the later Chola period down to the early fifteenth century, the paper argues that the appearance and rise of publicly witnessed and inscribed compacts drew on protocols (both ritual and documentary) that were associated with both royal courts and brahmanical assemblies. Particular attention is paid to inscriptional protocols for staging "presence" as a part of binding authority. The paper argues that the deployment of such protocols by new social agents toward the end of Chola

rule—where witnessed agreements were solemnized by the public documentary culture of the age—suggests that technologies of power associated with the royal court and its agrarian clients gradually evolved into a set of appropriate practices that could even be turned against the state that initiated them.

Résumé

L'essor des accords contractuels épigraphiques dans l'Inde du Sud médiévale

Cet essai examine l'histoire et l'importance des accords politiques conclus entre seigneurs, vassaux et groupes d'entreprises locaux dans l'Inde du Sud médiévale. Se concentrant principalement sur les documents d'inscription des terres du centre et du centre-nord de l'empire Chola, de la fin de la période Chola jusqu'au début du xv^e siècle, l'article soutient que l'essor des accords contractuels exposés et inscrits publiquement reposait sur des protocoles (rituels et documentaires) qui étaient associés aux cours royales et aux assemblées brahmaniques. Une attention particulière est accordée aux protocoles d'inscription visant à mettre en scène la « présence » dans le cadre d'une autorité contraignante. L'article affirme que le déploiement de tels protocoles par de nouveaux agents sociaux vers la fin du règne Chola – où des témoignages concordants ont été célébrés par la culture documentaire publique de l'époque – suggère que les technologies du pouvoir associées à la cour royale et à ses clients agraires ont progressivement évolué vers un ensemble de pratiques appropriées qui pouvaient même se retourner contre l'État qui les avait initiées.

